

IMPACT OF LIFE INSURANCE BUSINESS ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA

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Key words:

*Business,
Economic,
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Insurance,
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Abstract: *The study investigated the impact of life insurance business on economic growth in Nigeria, using time-series data from 2007 to 2024. The specific objectives of the study were to: find out the impact of total life insurance premiums on the gross domestic product of Nigeria; determine the impact of total life insurance claims on the gross domestic product of Nigeria; and examine the impact of total life insurance assets on the gross domestic product of Nigeria. An ex post facto research design was adopted because the study was secondary research. While the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique was applied in assessing each hypothesis. Results of hypotheses test show that: total life insurance premiums, total life insurance claims, and total life insurance assets had a significant impact on gross domestic product in Nigeria. Based on the findings, it was concluded that the life insurance business has a significant impact on Nigeria's economic growth within the framework of the adopted model from 2007 to 2024. The study recommended that, to increase the total premium income of the Nigerian insurance industry, the National Insurance Commission (NAICOM) and other market associations in the Nigerian insurance industry should embark on an aggressive awareness campaign and enforcement of all compulsory insurances in Nigeria. Through this synergy, the life insurance sector will definitely generate more premium income and contribute significantly to economic growth in Nigeria. Insurance companies should endeavor to settle genuine claims promptly and should employ competent asset managers to oversee the management of their assets to help maximize returns on assets and also improve the financial intermediation role of the Nigerian insurance sector, which will, in the long run, translate into economic growth.*

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1.1 Introduction

The insurance sector has been widely acknowledged as an integral part of the economy. It provides a risk transfer mechanism by which the losses of the few are paid for, by the contributions of many. It is a safeguard against risk (Nwite, 2005). Ivamy (1979) from the legal perspective posits that “a contract of insurance in the widest sense of the term may be defined as a contract whereby one person, called the insurer undertakes, to pay compensation, in return for the agreed consideration called ‘premium’ to another person called the insured a sum of money, or its equivalent, on the happening of a specified event”. Life insurance is yet to become big business in Nigeria, and the services that emanated therefrom are tagged “unsought products” (Oladepo, 2019).

Many studies have paid attention to the linkage between insurance activity and economic growth using different econometric models thereby generating conflicting result [Etale, 2019; Nwafor, 2019; Ouedraogo, Guerineau & Sawadogo, 2018; Nwosa & Mustapha, 2018; Fadun & Shoyemi, 2018; Igbodika Nwabun, 2024; Ofoniofoni, et al., 2025; Ebo & Umoru, 2025; Chijuka & Imoseme, 2025]. The sector helps pool risk and reduces the impact of large losses on firms and households with a beneficial impact on output, investment, innovation, and competition. As financial intermediaries with long investment horizons, life insurance companies can contribute to the provision of

long-term finance and more effective risk management. Moreover, the insurance sector can also improve the efficiency of other segments of the financial sector, such as banking and bond markets, by enhancing the value of collateral through property insurance and reducing losses at default through credit guarantees and enhancements (Feyen & Roberto, 2011).

The extent to which a country’s insurance industry contributes to the financial sector and the economy in general depends on its level of development. Nigerian Insurance Industry ranks 5th in Africa and 71st in the world with \$1.64 billion premium representing 0.2 percent premium collected globally in 2018 (Atlas Magazine, 2019). Nigerian insurance industry in 2019 generated a total gross premium of N413.8 billion, according to statistics obtained from the insurance digest published by Nigerian Insurers Association (NIA, 2020). This represented an increase of N13.8 billion, compared with the N400 billion recorded in 2018. The report showed that the industry has sustained the path of marginal growth in the past three years. In 2018, it recorded 10 per cent growth in gross premium generation from N363 billion in 2017, to N400 billion in 2018. The industry in the last decade has grown to be the second largest in the Nigerian financial service sector after the banking sector. The industry’s assets were estimated at N1.1 trillion and its investment portfolio at N848.6 billion as at December, 2017 (Agusto & Co, 2017). The steady flow of long-term capital provided to the

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financial market by the insurance industry is crucial for the financial system as a whole, as it reduces market volatility and thus contributes considerably to the stability and functioning of the economy.

Insurers invest the premium income they receive, making them among the largest institutional investors. For life insurance companies in particular, the products they write are long-term in nature, for this reason, corresponding long-term investments are made and held to maturity. To operate profitably, insurers must earn more from premiums, which are invested across a range of asset classes, than they pay out in claims (Zacks, 2017). It is also pertinent to note that not all funds available to life insurance companies are devoted to certain assets or investments. Some proportions of insurance funds are kept liquid in banks as reserve and for day-to-day running of business activities of insurance companies. These must be in line with the provisions of section 20 to 24 of Nigerian Insurance Industry Reform Act, 2025 (NIIRA, 2025). By complying with these regulation and management of insurance funds, insurance companies transfer huge amount of funds to the capital market by way of investments, certain portions are used to settle claims and also part of the premium income is transferred to banks in various forms of deposits in accordance with a company's liquidity preference needs and policies. Evident from these narratives, one can aptly argue that life insurance business activities could enhance economic growth. It is therefore against this

backdrop that this study investigated the impact of life insurance business on economic growth in Nigeria from 2007-2024 using total life insurance premium, total life insurance claims and total life insurance assets as indicators of insurance business. While gross domestic product (GDP) was used to represent economic growth.

1.3 Research Objectives

The broad objective of the study is to investigate the impact of life insurance business on economic growth of Nigeria. While the specific objectives were, to:

1. find out the impact of total life insurance premium on gross domestic product of Nigeria;
2. determine the impact of total life insurance claims on gross domestic product of Nigeria;
3. examine the impact of total life insurance assets on gross domestic product of Nigeria;

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions were put forward in line with the objectives of the study:

1. What is the impact of total life insurance premium on gross domestic product of Nigeria?
2. What is the impact of total life insurance claims on gross domestic product of Nigeria?
3. What is the impact of total life insurance assets on gross domestic product of Nigeria?

1.5 Statement of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were proposed in null form to guide the study.

1. H01: Total life insurance premiums have no significant impact on gross domestic product of Nigeria;

2. H02: Total life insurance claims have no significant impact on gross domestic product of Nigeria;

3. H03: Total life insurance assets have no significant impact on gross domestic product of Nigeria;

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Life Insurance Business

According to Okhakia (2010), life assurance business is a contract on longevity of human life between the insurance company and the life assured wherein the insurer promises to pay a lump sum or agreed installment at maturity or prior death of the life assured, on the receipt of small installment payments/premiums on due date. Life assurance companies generally design and package different products to meet individual needs and these products include whole life policies (with or without profits), investment linked policies, group life policies, and health insurance scheme among others. Life policies are a contract between the insurer and the policyholder. The insurer receives the premium in exchange for paying out amounts determined under the contract in specified circumstances. Life Insurance Companies offer policies that provide financial protection against life-related risks such as death, disability, or retirement (NAICOM, 2025)

2.1.2 Life Insurance Premium

Samreena (2018) defines "premium" as the recurring payment an insured individual pays to an insurer to assume the risk of an insured event. According to Samreena (2018), the

premium amount for a life insurance policy depends on the insured's age, occupation, and health. An insurance premium is a payment to an insurer for loss protection. Regular premiums might be paid monthly, quarterly, semiannually, or annually. The policyholder's payment schedule determines when to pay the premium. A policyholder pays premium to an insurance provider in exchange for benefits in the case of a covered loss (Shodhganga, 2018).

2.1.3 Life Insurance Claims

Barry (2011) defines insurance claims as all activities geared towards monitoring insured's compensation, restitution, repayment or any other remedy for loss or damage or in respect of doing their obligations. Claims are all about insurance and insurance is about taking up the liability or risk of the insured against a loss and when this is done, the insured would in return get a claim as compensation for the loss (Williams, 2009). The Farlex Financial Dictionary (2009) defined claims as a formal request to an insurance company asking for a payment based on the terms of the insurance policy. It defined a claims form as a document or request filed by a policyholder stating that an insured event has occurred and that the insurance company should provide coverage. Insurance claim is a notification to an insurance company requesting payment of an amount due under the terms of the policy. Insurance claim is a right of the insured under a contract of insurance. The insurer promises to compensate the insured or nominees/assignees of the insured on happening of event or risk insured.

Disputes crop up in the payment of claim when the insurer and the insured understand the process of claims payment in a different way. It is obvious for the insurance company to protect and guard the interests of the policyholders. An insurance claim is the only way to officially apply for benefits under an insurance policy, but until the insurance company has assessed the situation it will remain only a claim, not a payout.

2.1.4 Life Insurance Assets

An asset is a resource with economic value that an individual, corporation, or country owns or controls with the expectation that it will provide a future benefit. Assets are reported on a company's balance sheet and are bought or created to increase a firm's value or benefit the firm's operations. An asset can be thought of as something that, in the future, can generate cash flow, reduce expenses, or improve sales, regardless of whether it's manufacturing equipment or a patent (Adam, 2021). An asset represents an economic resource for a company or represents access that other individuals or firms do not have. A right or other access is legally enforceable, which means economic resources can be used at a company's discretion, and its use can be precluded or limited by an owner. Insurance Assets in Nigeria are classified into Life and Non-life insurance assets. Assets of life insurance companies comprises of financial instruments, which are used to back-up for life insurance and annuities reserves and have been primarily built up from premiums received from policyholders and

earnings from investments. These assets consist of government securities, shares, bonds and stocks, real estate, mortgage loans, policy loans, other loans, outstanding premiums, cash and bank balances and other debtors (Nigeria Insurance Digest, 2019).

2.1.5 Economic Growth

Economic Growth Variables Concept Economic growth is the process by which the productive component of an economy grows over time, resulting in an increase in national income. Economic growth manifests itself as a gain in income, an expansion of the work force, an increase in the country's total capital stock, and an increase in trade and consuming capacity. The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of a country is a measure of its output's economic model. The economic growth of a country can be used to determine its financial health. Nigeria's economy is characterized by rapid expansion (Ntiamoah, et al., 2014). Economic growth is achieved through making optimal use of available resources and improving a country's production capacity, allowing for easier revenue redistribution amongst the population and society. Increased economic growth means more goods and services are produced, the unemployment rate is lower, there are more job opportunities, and the population's standard of living is higher (Ntiamoah, et al., 2014). For the most of the time since independence, the Nigerian economy has performed poorly. This could be due to a variety of issues confronting the country; however, the task of achieving economic recovery and sustained qualitative

growth appears to be daunting, as Nigeria appears to be sucked into a vortex of interlocking vicious articles that have interacted to keep the country in a low growth equilibrium trap (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2024).

2.1. 5 Conceptual Framework

The model in figure 2.1 is the conceptual framework adopted for this study. The

Dependent Variable is economic growth which is proxied with gross domestic product of Nigerian. While the independent variable life insurance business was decomposed into three key life insurance business activities: total life premium, total life insurance claims and total life Insurance assets.

**Dependent Variable
Economic Growth**

**Independent Variable
Life Insurance Business**

Fig. 2.1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Researcher’s conceptualization, 2025.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on Harrod-Domar economic growth model. The theory was developed independently by Roy F. Harrod in (1939) and Evsey Domar in 1946. This is otherwise called Harrod-Domar economic growth model. It stresses the importance of savings and investment as key determinants of growth. Harrod-Domar theory is a growth theory that assumes how efficient investment can be made to produce profit called capital gain. A growth theory helps to explain how growth has occurred and how it may occur again in the future through investment. Growth

strategies are the things a government might introduce to replicate the outcome suggested by the model using economic growth model. Basically, Harrod-Domar economic growth theory suggests that the economy rate of growth depends on; the level of national savings and the productivity of capital investment (known as the capital-output ratio). The basic Harrod-Domar model is rated growth of GDP as savings ratio/capital output ratio. If the savings rate is 10% and the capital output ratio is 2, then a country’s economy will grow at 5% per year. Based on the model therefore, the rate of growth in an economy can be increased in one of two

ways; increased level of savings in the economy (i.e. gross national savings as a% of GDP) and reducing the capital output ratio (i.e. increasing the quantity/productivity of capital input). Theoretically, the various channels through which insurance and pensions companies can positively impact economic growth include mobilization of domestic savings, efficient management of different risks, mitigation of losses, more efficient allocation of domestic capital and promotion of financial stability as well as efficient investment of pension and insurance funds (Acha and Ukpung, 2012). This theory is relevant to this study because life insurance encourages savings and investment, which in turn increases insurance output level, promotes capital market activities and can contribute to economic growth.

2.3 Empirical Review

2.3.1 Life Insurance Premium and Economic Growth

Ouedraogo, et al. (2018) investigated the association between the development of the life insurance sector and economic growth in 86 developing countries using data spanning 1996 to 2011 obtained from World Development Indicators compiled by the World Bank. They adopted total life insurance premium as the explanatory variable and GDP (proxy for economic growth) as the response variable. The study employed descriptive statistics, generalized moments method (GMM) for the analysis of data. The results indicated that insurance sector development had positive effect on economic growth, but it varies from

country to country according to the structural characteristics of different countries.

Fadun and Oluwaleye (2023) explored the development of life insurance and economic growth using Nigeria as a case study from 2000 to 2022. Data used for the study were collected from sources including the World Development Indicator database, Global Financial Development Indicator database, NIA digest database, and Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin. The investigation approach used the Granger causality test and Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) co-integration. The Granger causality test result indicated that there is no causal connection between Nigeria's economic growth and the development of life insurance. According to ARDL's estimated results, life insurance density and penetration had a negligible positive effect on the real GDP growth rate. This finding revealed that life insurance development did not contribute to Nigeria's economic growth from 2000 to 2022. Dada et al. (2023) studied the effect of insurance on Nigerian economic growth from 2007 to 2021 using Ex-post facto analytical research design. While Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression technique was used to analyze the data. According to the findings, non-life gross premium has a considerable positive influence on real GDP, life gross premium has no significant effect on real GDP, and there is a significant positive association between total insurance gross premium and economic growth in Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study concluded that insurance and economic growth

in Nigeria have a considerable positive association.

Oke, et al. (2024) examined the nexus between insurance sector and economic growth in Nigeria from 1985 to 2022 using ordinary least square and pairwise granger causality as estimated technique. The result revealed that there is no causal relationship between investment (LIINV) and gross domestic product (LNGDP), there is a unidirectional relationship from LNGDP to LNLP, and also, there is no causal relationship between LNGDP to LNNLP. Also, there is a unidirectional relationship from LNINFR to LNGDP. The direction of the flow comes from gross domestic product to life premium in Nigeria.

Ofoniofoni, et al. (2025) focused attention on life and non-life insurance activities independently and their economic impact in Nigeria from 1990 to 2024. The empirical study was conducted using descriptive statistics. The Johansen cointegration test confirms a long-term relationship among life insurance, non-life insurance, and economic performance. The long-run and short-run dynamics (ECM) indicate a positive and significant effect between life insurance gross premiums and gross domestic product. The gross premium of non-life insurance exerts a positive yet insignificant influence on gross domestic product. Total assets in general insurance demonstrate a positive but insignificant effect on gross domestic product. The research therefore concludes that life and non-life insurance

activities independently influence economic performance in Nigeria.

Chijuka and Imoseme (2025) examined the relationship between the insurance sector and economic growth in Nigeria (1985-2024), focusing on insurance investment, life insurance premiums, non-life insurance premiums, and inflation rate. Using VECM and Granger causality test, the study analyzes both long-run and short-run interactions. The VECM results reveal that GDP growth (-0.421, $p = 0.001$) has a significant speed of adjustment, meaning that any deviation from the long-run equilibrium corrects itself at a rate of 42.1% per year. Insurance investment (-0.278, $p = 0.005$) significantly contributes to economic growth, adjusting back to equilibrium at 27.8% per year. Non-life insurance premiums (-0.365, $p = 0.002$) and life insurance premiums (-0.214, $p = 0.008$) exhibit strong long-run relationships with GDP, with adjustment rates of 36.5% and 21.4% per year, respectively. Inflation (-0.132, $p = 0.049$) is marginally significant, playing a role in long-run adjustments but at a slower rate of 13.2% per year. The Granger causality test confirms bi-directional causality between GDP growth and insurance sector variables, reinforcing a mutually reinforcing relationship between economic expansion and insurance sector development.

2.3.2 Insurance Claims and Economic Growth

Monogbe (2015) investigated the effect of insurance sector development on the growth of Nigerian economy from 1981-2013 using

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Ordinary Least Square method, Augmented Dickey Fuller test, Descriptive statistics, co-integration and granger causality test. The results indicated that there exists a long run equilibrium association between insurance sector development and growth. Total insurance investment had a positive and significant association to economic growth, while insurance premium was also positively and significantly associated to economic growth. It was found that causality flows from GDP to some insurance sector development indicators (TIP, TIN, and TIR). It was further revealed that insurance claims had a significant but negative association to economic growth. The study recommends that law makers and NAICOM should look into the claims payment policy of insurance companies so as to ensure transparency, avoid extortion and ensure fair dealings in order to actualize the sector's objective and hence promote economic growth of our country Nigeria.

Gabriel (2015) investigated the effect of insurance sector development on economic growth in Nigeria using time series data obtained from CBN Statistical Bulletin for the period 1981 to 2013. The study adopted GDP (proxy for economic growth) as the response variable, while insurance sector development indicators such as total insurance claims, total insurance premium, total insurance investment and total insurance returns were used as the predictive variables. Descriptive statistics, multiple regression (based on OLS), ADF unit root test, unrestricted co-integration test and

Granger causality test were the statistical tools employed for the analysis of data. The results revealed that total insurance investment and total insurance premium had significant positive link with GDP, while total insurance claims had significant negative effect on GDP. The study concluded that insurance sector development had strong effect on economic growth in Nigeria. Fadun and Osasona (2024) analyzed the impact of life insurance claim settlement on insurance penetration rate in Nigeria using time series data from 2000 to 2023. The study's data was analyzed using charts and the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model co-integration technique. The findings showed that, although the insurance penetration rate fluctuated, both the amount of life insurance claims paid and the insurance penetration rate in Nigeria showed an upward trend from 2000 to 2023. Additionally, the study confirmed that life insurance claims significantly influenced Nigeria's insurance penetration rate, though negatively over the long term. The study concluded that life insurance claim settlement plays significant role on insurance penetration in Nigeria.

Asogwa and Munyenembe (2025) examined the impact of insurance claim settlement on economic growth in Nigeria. This study used an annual time series data ranging from 1990 to 2023. The study employed autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model to analyze the time series data. Finding from the ARDL regression result showed that; the coefficients of life assurance (LIA) and fire insurance (FIN) were positive and insignificant to gross domestic

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product (GDP) while motor insurance (MIO) and oil and gas insurance (OGI) were positive and insignificant to gross domestic product.

Ebo and Umoru (2025) evaluated the correlation between insurance market operations and economic performance in Nigeria. Data were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). The study reported that, the offering of financial protection has a strong positive relationship with economic performance ($r = 0.7187$; $R^2 = 51.66\%$), investment of premium funds exhibited an even stronger correlation ($r = 0.8079$; $R^2 = 65.27\%$) while provision of foreign insurance services has a moderately meaningful relationship ($r = 0.5230$; $R^2 = 27.36\%$). These various findings underscores that the Nigerian insurance sector plays a crucial stabilizing and contributing meaningfully to the Nigerian economy.

2.3.3 Life Insurance Assets and Economic Growth

Ching, et al. (2010) examined the causal effect of life insurance assets on economic growth. This was experimented using the co-integration analysis with quarterly data drawn from Malaysia for the period 1997 to 2008. On the whole, the evidence, particularly from the regression result seems to suggest that there is a one-way relationship flowing from real GDP to life insurance sector. No causal relationship flowed from life insurance to GDP. This shows that the response by the economy growth indicators to life insurance sector variables like savings mobilization, risk management and

investment do not completely grow the economy.

Thanga, et al. (2023) investigated the relationship between the life insurance sector and the economy in Indian economy over a forty-year period (1981-2020). Their findings highlight the significance of the life insurance sector in contributing to economic growth and the importance of considering this relationship in economic and financial planning.

Mouna (2024) analyzed the relationship between life insurance market development and economic growth in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region. The study examines data from 15 countries over the period from 1999 to 2023 using panel unit root tests, panel cointegration inquiries and pooled mean group (PMG) estimation to uncover potential causal relationships. The results demonstrate a substantial and positive long-term relationship between the life insurance sector and economic growth in the MENA region. This long-term connection suggests that advancements and expansions within the life insurance industry are significantly associated with, and potentially contribute to, overall economic growth in the region.

2.3.4 Gap in Empirical Review

One of the major gaps that necessitated this study centered on currency of data and the period of study. This study is unique because it investigated the impact of life insurance business on economic growth in Nigeria from 2007 to 2024.

Secondly, results from empirical review carried out showed contradicting results. It therefore became imperative to carry out this study using a different methodology.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research design

The researcher adopted an *ex-post facto* research design to investigate the impact of life insurance business on economic growth in Nigeria. This is a type of research design whereby the investigation starts after the fact has occurred without interference from the researcher. This is a type of research which aims at determining or establishing or measuring the relationship between one variable and another or the effect of one variable on another, in which the variables involved are not manipulated by the researcher (Onwumere, 2020). The choice of this research design was based on the fact that the researcher utilized secondary data (historical data or time series data) to carry out this study.

3.2 Area of Study

This study titled the impact of life insurance business on economic growth was carried out in Nigeria using time series data from 2007 to 2024. The study focused on financial sector of the Nigerian economy with particular interest on Nigerian life insurance sub-sector and economic growth of Nigeria.

3.3 Nature and sources of Data

Secondary data were used to carry out this study. Data were sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin, Insurance Digest

and National Insurance Commission's annual publication of various years.

3.4 Model specification

The researcher adopted a model from the study carried out by Onwumere, Ibe, Ozor and Mounanu, (2012) which was stated as follows:

$$EG=f(BMV, MSD, ED, SMC) \quad - \quad - (i)$$

$$EG= \beta_0 + \beta_1 BMV t_1 + \beta_2 MSD t_2 + \beta_3 ED t_3 + \beta_4 SMC t_4. + \mu t \quad - \quad - \quad (ii)$$

The above model was modified to adequately capture the objectives of the study. Thus, the functional relation of the model was given as follows:

$$GDP = f(TLIP, TLIC, TLIA) \quad - \quad - \quad (iii)$$

The regression model will be specified as:

$$GDPT = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TLIPt_1 + \beta_2 TLIC t_2 + \beta_3 TLIA t_3 + \mu t \quad - \quad - \quad (iii)$$

The general model was disintegrated into model one, two and three in order to capture the specific objectives and hypotheses of the study.

Model One for Hypothesis one

H01: Total life insurance premium had no significant effect on economic growth (GDP) in Nigeria.

The functional relation of the model was given as:

$$M2/GDP = f(TLIP) \quad (iv)$$

While its regression model was specified as:

$$GDPT = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TLIP Pt_1 + \mu t \quad - \quad (v)$$

Where:

GDPT = Gross Domestic Product (Economic growth),

TLIP = Total Life insurance premium

β_0 = Constant

β_1 = Slope coefficient,

μ = the error term

Model Two for Hypothesis Two

Ho2: Total life insurance claims had no significant effect on economic growth (GDP) in Nigeria.

The functional relation of the model was given as:

$$M2/GDP = f(TLIC) \quad (vi)$$

While its regression model was specified as:

$$M2/GDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TLIC_t + \mu_t \quad (vii)$$

Where:

GDP_t = Gross Domestic Product (Economic growth),

TLIC = Total Life Insurance Claims

β_0 = Constant

β_1 = Slope coefficient,

μ = the error term

Model Three for Hypothesis Three

Ho3: Total life insurance claims had no significant effect on economic growth (GDP) in Nigeria

The functional relation of the model was given as:

$$GDP = f(TLIA) \quad - \quad (viii)$$

While its regression model was specified as:

$$GDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TLIA_t + \mu_t \quad - \quad (ix)$$

Where:

GDP = Gross Domestic Product (Economic growth)

Table 4.2: Descriptive Statistics of the variables studied

	GDP	TLIP	TLIC	TLIA
Mean	16.06462	0.389743	3.896427	4.985283
Median	13.25043	0.380000	3.973830	5.094357
Maximum	25.15527	0.611000	5.286641	6.304829

TINV = Total Life Insurance Assets,

β_0 = Constant

β_1 = Slope coefficient,

μ = the error term

3.8 Method of Data analysis

Data used for this study were first subjected to test of stationarity using Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test. Test of normality was conducted using Jacque-Bera test. Thereafter, a test of Model adequacy was carried out. This was estimated using Coefficient of Correlation (R²) and Adjusted Coefficient of Determination (AR²) and Durbin Watson parameters. The Coefficient of Correlation (R) points to a high or low linear relationship between the dependent and independent variable. The Adjusted Coefficient of Determination (AR²) is a modified version of R². It indicates how well terms fit a curve or line, but adjusts for the number of terms in a model. Then, ARDL regression method was used to test the hypotheses. An autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model is an ordinary least square (OLS) based model which is applicable for both non-stationary time series as well as for times series with mixed order of integration.

4.0 DATA ANALYSIS

4.1 Descriptive statistics

The descriptive statistics of the variables used in the study are presented in table 4.2.

Minimum	9.152900	0.290000	1.936514	3.410946
Std. Dev.	5.345223	0.074110	1.028623	0.937962
Skewness	0.427470	1.284516	-0.324344	-0.311924
Kurtosis	1.498570	4.355713	1.934479	1.698433
Jarque-Bera	4.353440	12.30524	2.269359	3.038093
Probability	0.113413	0.002128	0.321525	0.218921
Sum	562.2615	13.64100	136.3749	174.4849
Sum Sq. Dev.	971.4278	0.186739	35.97420	29.91229
Observations	18	18	18	18

Source: E-View 10.0 Output, 2025

Table 4.2 indicates that the average value of gross domestic product (GDP) was 16.06464 with a standard deviation of 5.345223. The minimum and maximum values stood at 9.152900 and 25.15527 respectively.

The average value of total life insurance premium was 0.389743 with a standard deviation of 0.074110. The maximum and minimum values stood at 0.611000 and 9.15290000 respectively. This indicates that for every ₦1 held as the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in Nigeria, the Nigerian insurance industry contributed ₦0.389743. The lower positive values of maximum and minimum total life insurance premium indicates that the industry has positive impact on GDP but the penetration is very low.

In addition, total life insurance claims settlement measured in longitudinal form has the average value of 3.896427 with a standard

deviation of 1.028623. The maximum and minimum values stood at 5.286641 and 1.936514 respectively. This implies that on the average, 3.896427 claims were settled which contribute to economic growth in Nigeria.

The total life insurance asset has the average value of 4.985283 with a standard deviation of 0.937962. The maximum and minimum values stood at 6.304829 and 3.410946 measured in longitudinal form respectively. This means that on the average, the life insurance industry assets contribute 4.985283 to economic growth in Nigeria.

4.2.2 Correlation Matrix

One of the preconditions of running regression is to ensure that data collected for the study is free from several multicollinearity. To achieve this purpose, bivariate correlation was carried out to check multicollinearity problem. Table 4.2 presents the relevant correlation matrix:

Table 4.3: Correlation Matrix

	TLIP	TLIC	TLIA
TINP	1.000000	-0.508758	-0.542044
TINC	-0.508758	1.000000	0.979274
TINA	-0.542044	0.979274	1.000000

Source: E-View 10.0, 2025

Table 4.3 presents the correlation matrix of all the explanatory variables used in the study and they include: total life insurance premium (TLIP), total life insurance claims (TLIC) and total life insurance assets (TLIA). As shown in table 4.2, the coefficient of all the variables were less than 1.00, meaning that the data for the study were free from multicollinearity as recommended by Brooks (2008) (as cited in Suleiman, 2013).

4.3 Statistical Diagnosis Test of Residuals

Another important requirement for valid regression is carrying out diagnostic tests to

Table 4.4 Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Unit Root Test

Variable	ADF Statistic	Critical Value @ 5%	P-Value	Order of Integration
GDP	-2.519851	-3.552973	0.3172	I(0)
TLIP	-3.005497	-3.54849	0.1455	I(0)
TINC	-4.260204	-3.54809	0.0098	I(1)
TINA	-0.656284	-3.54849	0.9685	I(0)

Source: E-View 10.0 Output, 2025

Table 4.4 contains the result of Augmented Dickey Fuller unit root test. GDP, TLIP, and TLIA were all integrated at order I(0) while TINC is integrated at order I(1). Given these different orders of integration, the Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model (ARDL)

ensure stationarity of the data as well as robustness of regression. The pre-estimation includes stationarity test and normality test. The test of stationarity was carried out using Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test. While normality test was conducted using Jacque-Bera test.

4.3.1. Stationarity Test for Unit Root

To ensure stationarity of the data used in the study, the study conducted the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test and the stationarity tests output data are shown in Table 4.3.

which tolerates such stationary property combination will be used. In addition, the sample size is also good enough for the ARDL given that its estimates remain robust and consistent in the face of large sample size and finally good for data characterized with

structural brakes. Also, the variable were log transformed to bring down the data size and ensure linearity. The alternate hypotheses of a unit root which stated that the variables of interest must be statically significant and that the test statistic must be more negative than the critical value at 5%. Thus, the result of stationary of unit root test using ADF illustrated in table 4.4 indicates that all the variables are stationary at levels based on order of integration.

Table 4.5 Jarque-Bera Normality Test

Model	Jarque Statistic	Bera	P-Value	Normality of Distribution
1	4.353440		0.113413	Normally Distributed
2	2.955698		0.228128	Normally Distributed
3	2.269359		0.321525	Normally Distributed

Source: E-View 10.0 Output, 2025

Table 4.5 indicates the Jarque-Bera normality tests for all the variables used in the study. The Jarque-Bera statistics for all variables used in models 1, 2 and 3, were 4.353440, 2.955698 and 2.269359 respectively with corresponding p-values of 0.113413, 0.228128 and 0.321525 each. Thus, the p-values are greater than 0.05 (5%) as required. Therefore, the residuals of the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, and 4th models were normally distributed. Gupta (2013) states that the result of normality holds true even if the population from which the samples are drawn is not normal provided the sample size is sufficient enough as stated in the central limit theorem. The central

4.3.2 Normality Tests

The models used in the study were subjected to normality test to ensure that error term is normally distributed. The output data are shown in the Appendix. The decision rule for accepting the null hypothesis is that if the p-value of Jarque-Bera statistic is greater than 0.05, we have no enough statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis. The extracts from the Appendix E are depicted in Table 4.5.

limit theorem holds the view that when more samples are taken, the graph of the sample mean will look like normal distribution.

4.4 Test of Hypotheses

4.4.1 Test of Hypothesis One

Restatement of Hypothesis one in null and alternate forms.

Ho: Total life insurance premium had no significant impact on gross domestic product in Nigeria.

H1: Total life insurance premium had significant impact on gross domestic product in Nigeria.

Table 4.6: Result For Test of Hypothesis One

Dependent Variable: GDP

Method: ARDL

Date: 10/31/25 Time: 20:30

Sample (adjusted): 2 18

Included observations: 16 after adjustments

Maximum dependent lags: 1 (Automatic selection)

Model selection method: Akaike info criterion (AIC)

Dynamic regressors (1 lag, automatic): TLIP

Fixed regressors: C

Number of models evaluated: 2

Selected Model: ARDL(1, 0)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
GDP(-1)	0.881665	0.065980	13.36271	0.0000
TLIP	-10.67253	4.643366	-2.298447	0.0284
C	6.388592	2.544386	2.510858	0.0175
R-squared	0.906157	Mean dependent var		16.19132
Adjusted R-squared	0.900102	S.D. dependent var		5.371989
S.E. of regression	1.697902	Akaike info criterion		3.980761
Sum squared resid	89.36901	Schwarz criterion		4.115440
Log likelihood	-64.67294	Hannan-Quinn criter.		4.026690
F-statistic	149.6691	Durbin-Watson stat		1.980191
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			
R-squared	0.906157			

Source: Author's calculation using E-views 10, 2025

Decision Criteria

Accept the null hypothesis if p-value of (t-statistic) is greater than 0.05 level of significance otherwise accept the alternate hypothesis.

Estimated Model Result for Hypothesis one

Using the extract of empirical results from table 4.6 for test of hypothesis one. The ARDL regression result showed that the coefficient was -10.67253; the t-statistic was -2.298447; and its p-value was [0.0284].

Decision: Since the level of significance [0.05] is higher than the p-values [0.0284], the alternate hypothesis was accepted because there was no enough statistical evidence to accept the null hypothesis. Hence, it was concluded that total life insurance premium had significant impact on gross domestic product (GDP) in Nigeria.

4.4.2 Test of Hypothesis Two

Table 4.7: Result for Test of Hypothesis Two

Dependent Variable: GDP

Method: ARDL

Date: 10/31/25 Time: 21:41

Sample (adjusted): 2 18

Included observations: 16 after adjustments

Maximum dependent lags: 1 (Automatic selection)

Model selection method: Akaike info criterion (AIC)

Dynamic regressors (0 lag, automatic): TLIC

Fixed regressors: C

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
GDP(-1)	0.777403	0.100598	7.727804	0.0000
TLIC	1.190005	0.538297	2.210687	0.0346
C	-0.836188	1.239832	-0.674436	0.5050
R-squared	0.905122	Mean dependent var		16.19132
Adjusted R-squared	0.899001	S.D. dependent var		5.371989
S.E. of regression	1.707238	Akaike info criterion		3.991728
Sum squared resid.	90.35447	Schwarz criterion		4.126406
Log likelihood	-64.85937	Hannan-Quinn criter.		4.037657
F-statistic	147.8677	Durbin-Watson stat		1.810950
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			
R-squared	0.905122			

Source: E-views 10 Output, 2025

Restatement of Hypothesis Two in null and alternate forms.

Ho: Total life insurance claims had no significant impact on gross domestic product (GDP) in Nigeria.

H1: Total life insurance claims had significant impact on gross domestic product (GDP) in Nigeria.

Decision Criteria: Accept the null hypothesis if p-value of (t-statistic) is greater than 0.05 level of significance otherwise accept the alternate hypothesis.

Estimated Model Result for Hypothesis Two

Using the extract of empirical results from table 4.7 for test of hypothesis two. The ARDL regression result showed that the coefficient was 1.190005; the t-statistic was 2.210687; and its p-value was [0.0346].

Decision: Since the level of significance [0.05] is higher than the p-values [0.0346], it was

Table 4.10: Result for Test of Hypothesis Three

Dependent Variable: GDP

Method: ARDL

Date: 10/31/25 Time: 21:43

Sample (adjusted): 2 18

Included observations: 16 after adjustments

Maximum dependent lags: 1 (Automatic selection)

Model selection method: Akaike info criterion (AIC)

Dynamic regressors (0 lag, automatic): TLIA

Fixed regressors: C

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
GDP(-1)	0.775882	0.096749	8.019560	0.0000
TLIA	1.316860	0.560044	2.351350	0.0252
C	-2.732606	1.822536	-1.499343	0.1439
R-squared	0.906789	Mean dependent var		16.19132
Adjusted R-squared	0.900775	S.D. dependent var		5.371989
S.E. of regression	1.692175	Akaike info criterion		3.974004
Sum squared resid	88.76718	Schwarz criterion		4.108683
Log likelihood	-64.55807	Hannan-Quinn criter.		4.019934
F-statistic	150.7890	Durbin-Watson stat		1.817885

concluded that total life insurance claims had significant impact on gross domestic product (GDP) in Nigeria.

4.4.3 Test of Hypothesis Three

Restatement of Hypothesis three in null and alternate forms.

Ho: Total life insurance assets had no significant impact on gross domestic product (GDP) in Nigeria. H1: Total life insurance assets had significant impact on gross domestic product (GDP) in Nigeria.

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Prob(F-statistic) 0.000000

R-squared 0.905122

Source: E-views 10 Output, 2025

Decision Criteria

Accept the null hypothesis if p-value of (t-statistic) is greater than 0.05 level of significance otherwise accept the alternate hypothesis.

Estimated Model Result for Hypothesis Three

Using the extract of empirical results from table 4.10 for test of hypothesis three. The ARDL regression result showed that the coefficient was

1.316860; the t-statistic was 2.351350; and its p-value was [0.0252].

Decision: Since the level of significance [0.05] is higher than the p-value [0.0252], the alternate hypothesis was accepted because there was not enough statistical evidence to accept the null hypothesis. Thus, it was concluded that Total life insurance assets had no significant impact on gross domestic product (GDP) in Nigeria.

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4.5 Discussion of Result from the Test of Hypotheses

4.5.1: Result from test of hypothesis One

The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) result for test of hypothesis one which had P-value of 0.0284 indicates that total life insurance premium had significant impact on gross domestic product (GDP) in Nigeria between 2007 to 2024. This result corroborates with the following studies: Ouedraogo, et al. (2018) who investigated the association between the development of the life insurance sector and economic growth in 86 developing countries and found that life insurance sector development had positive effect on economic growth, but it varies from country to country. In the same vein, Oke, et al. (2024); Ofoniofoni, et al. (2025) and Chijuka and Imoseme (2025) found that life insurance premium have significant association with economic growth. However, contradicts the results of Fadun and Oluwaleye (2023) and Dada et al. (2023) who found that life insurance gross premium has no significant effect on real GDP in Nigeria.

4.5.2: Results from test of Hypothesis Two

The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) result for test of hypothesis two which had P-value of 0.03461 indicates that total life insurance claims had significant impact on gross domestic product (GDP) in Nigeria between 2007 to 2024. This result corroborates with the following studies: Fadun and Osasona (2024) and Ebo and Umoru (2025) who also found strong positive relationship with economic

performance in Nigeria. Moreover, kue-John and Nwantah (2019) who analysed insurance industry and economic growth in Nigeria between 1980 and 2015 using Ordinary Least Square (OLS) multiple regression techniques found that the claim expenditure of the insurance industry showed a positive relationship with economic growth in the long run. This study in terms of magnitude contradicts the finding of Asogwa and Munyenyembe (2025) examined the impact of insurance claim settlement on economic growth in Nigeria and found that life insurance claims had positive and insignificant association to gross domestic product (GDP) in Nigeria. This result however, contradicts with the findings of Gabriel (2015) and Monogbe (2015) who found that total insurance claims had significant negative effect on GDP.

4.5.3: Results from test of Hypothesis Three

The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) result for test of hypothesis three which had P-value of 0.0252 indicates that total life insurance assets had significant impact on gross domestic product (GDP) in Nigeria between 2007 to 2024. This result was contrary to the findings of Ching, Kogid and Furuoka (2010) that studied the effect of life insurance assets on economic growth in Malaysia for the period 1997 to 2008 and found out that no causal relationship flowed from life insurance assets to GDP.

5.0 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings

The following were the findings of the study based on the test of hypotheses carried out in chapter four. It was discovered that:

1. Total life insurance premium had significant impact on gross domestic product in Nigeria. This finding was arrived at based on the p-value of 0.0284 from model one.
2. Total life insurance claims had significant impact on gross domestic product in Nigeria. This result was arrived at based on the p-value of 0.0346 from model two.
3. Total life insurance assets had significant impact on gross domestic product in Nigeria. This finding was arrived at based on the p-value of 0.0252 from model three.

5.2 Conclusion

This study investigated the impact of life insurance business on economic growth of Nigeria from 2007 to 2024. Life insurance business was decomposed into: total life insurance premium, total life insurance claims and total life insurance assets. While economic growth was proxied with gross domestic product (GDP). Based on the findings from the analysis of data and test of hypotheses done, it was concluded that life insurance business have significant impact on the economic growth of Nigeria within the framework of the adopted model from 2007 to 2024.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made in line with the findings and conclusion of the study.

1. In order to increase total premium income of the Nigerian insurance industry, National Insurance Commission (NAICOM) and other market associations in the Nigerian insurance industry should embark on aggressive awareness campaign and enforcement of all compulsory insurances in Nigeria. This can be achieved through a collaborative drive between NAICOM and relevant security agencies with the support of government both at The Federal and State levels. Through this synergy, life insurance sector will definitely generate more premium income and contribute significantly to economic growth in Nigeria.
2. Insurance companies should endeavour to settle genuine claims promptly. While the Nigerian insurance industry regulators should enhance its supervisory frameworks to ensure that genuine claims are promptly settled by insurance companies.
3. Insurance companies should employ competent assets manager to oversee the management of their assets in line with the liquidity preference needs of the company. This will help to maximize returns on assets and also improve the financial intermediation role of Nigerian insurance sector which will in the long run translate into economic growth.

5.4 Contribution to Knowledge

This study has shown how life insurance business impacted on economic growth of Nigeria from 2007 to 2024. Therefore, the

findings of this study will be useful to insurance practitioner, insurance industry regulators, government and the apex financial system regulators. The outcome of this study will help them to understand the impact of life insurance

References

Asogwa, O.J. & Munyenyembe, U.C (2025). "Insurance Claim Settlement and Economic Growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 9(2), 2172-2180.

Chijuka I. M. & Imoseme M. I. (2025). Insurance Sector Development and Economic Growth in Nigeria: The Role of Inflation and Investment Dynamics. *UNIBEN Journal of Marketing*, 4(1); 308-329.

Ching, K. S., Kogid, M., & Mulok, D. (2010). Insurance funds and economic growth in Malaysia: Further empirical evidence. *Interdisciplinary Review of Economics and Management*, 1(1), 1-9.

Dada, D.A., Ibitomi, T., Aderotimi B., & Gaude-Jiwul P.S. (2023). Insurance Premium and the Growth of Nigeria Economy. *European Journal of Business and Innovation Research*, 11(6), 14-32.

Egbeonu, O.C. (2016). Insurance investment portfolio and economic development in Nigeria: a co-integration analysis. *International Journal of Advances*

business on economic growth of Nigeria. In addition, the study to knowledge by providing a vital source of literature to future researchers who may wish to carry out further research on this topic or related areas.

Academic Research in Social and Management Sciences, 2(5), 22-31.

Ebo & Umoru, B. (2025). Insurance Market Operations and Economic Performance in Nigeria: An Empirical Insight. *International Journal of Innovative Finance and Economic Research*. 13(3); 293-303.

Etale, L. M. (2019). Insurance sector development and economic growth in Nigeria: An Empirical Analysis. *International Journal of Development and Economic Sustainability*, 7(4), 34-48.

Fadun, O. S., & Oluwaleye, T. O. (2023). Impact of life insurance development on economic growth: A case study of Nigeria (2000-2022). *GUSAU Journal of Economics and Development Studies*, 4(1), 162-181.

Fadun, O. S., & Osasona, A. V. (2024). Roles of life insurance claim settlement on insurance penetration in Nigeria. *GUSAU Journal of Economics and Development Studies*, 5(1), 310-325. <https://doi.org/10.57233/Gujeds.V5i1>.

Fadun, O. S., & Shoyemi, O. S. (2018). Insurance investment funds and economic growth in

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- Nigeria: An empirical analysis. *International Journal of Development and Management Review*, 13(1), 73-88.
- Gabriel, M. T. (2015) Impact of insurance sector development on the growth of Nigeria economy. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research - Social Sciences and Education*, 1(2), 1-20.
- Mouna Z. (2024). Life Insurance and Economic Growth Nexus: Evidence from The MENA region. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 16(9), 23-30.
- Nwabun, A.I. (2024). Effect of Insurance Funds on Human Development Index in Nigeria. *Texila International Journal of Academic Research*, 2(1); 1-14.
- Ofoniofoni, S. B., Aleibiri, E. & Obentey, A. A. (2025). Diagnosis of Life and Non-Life Insurance Sector on Economic Growth in Nigeria: Impact and Feasibility. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Management*, 10(12); 145-153.
- Oke, M.O., Fayomi, E. J. & Ayorinde, B. F. (2024). The Nexus between Insurance Sector and Economic Growth in Nigeria. *FUOYE Journal of Accounting and Management*, 7(1), 378-389
- Onwumere, J. U. J. (2020). *Business, economic and social research methods*. Enugu, Immaculate Publications Limited.
- Ouedraogo, I., Guerineau, S., & Sawadogo, R. (2018). Life insurance development and economic growth: Evidence from developing countries. *Journal of Economic Development*, 43(2), 1- 28.
- Thanga, J. L. T., Lalremruati, A., Lalmuanpuia (2023). Relationship between Economic Growth and Life Insurance: The Determining Factors of Life Insurance Policy Demand in India. *Journal of Law and Sustainable Development*, 11(9), 10-52.
- Torbira, L. (2018). Insurance risk management: a correlate of economic growth in Nigeria. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 9(7), 1-10.

Okeke, Daniel Chukwudi, Ph.D. and Agbaji, Benjamin Chukwuma, Ph.D